

Conference Abstract

Propagation and conservation of crucian carp in Hungary: insights from laboratory, semi-intensive, and pond rearing

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Abstract

We first began working on the propagation and rearing of the crucian carp (*Carassius carassius*) in 2002, when our initial stockings also took place. More intensive research started in 2007, focusing on issues related to the reproduction and rearing of the species under laboratory, semi-intensive, and pond farming conditions. Within induced spawning cycles, we examined the effects of egg treatment (Woynarovich solution combined with tannin treatment) and different incubation temperatures on reproductive parameters, as well as on embryo and larval development. In a series of larval rearing experiments, we compared various feeding strategies, including the use of commercially available feeds, live feed, and different combinations of both. We also determined the optimal weaning strategy to achieve optimal survival and growth for an economically feasible production. During intensive juvenile rearing (up to the one-summer-old stage), we carried out experiments to evaluate different feeding regimes, to determine optimal feed rations, and to assess the role of live feed supplementation in survival and growth, with special attention to the occurrence of deformities. In pond-based trials, we investigated the possibilities of monoculture rearing of crucian carp and co-rearing with tench (*Tinca tinca*) in nursery ponds and pond-cage systems. We also studied the development of restocked populations at the “*Umbra krameri*” species protection area. In a separate series of experiments, we monitored the migration patterns of tagged crucian carp in

Lake Balaton. Additionally, we conducted morphometric comparisons of crucian carp, Prussian carp (*Carassius auratus gibelio*), and their hybrids, as well as population studies in habitats where all three genotypes occur. In the course of our work, we have so far restocked 150,000 individuals (larvae, juveniles, and sexually mature individuals). Our research is ongoing, with a special focus on developing rearing protocols and feeding strategies tailored to the species' needs to support effective conservation and restocking programs.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.